

Epicardial high-density electrogram mapping dynamics during Pulsed Field Ablation (PFA)

Tomás García-Sánchez¹, Gerard Amorós-Figueras², Sergi Casabella-Ramon³, Zoraida Moreno-Weidmann², Jose M. Guerra² and Antoni Ivorra^{1,4}

¹ Department of Information and Communication Technologies, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, Spain

² Department of Cardiology, Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau, Institut d'Investigació Biomèdica - Sant Pau, CIBERCV, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

³ IIB Sant Pau, Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau, Instituto de Investigaciones Biomédicas de Barcelona, CSIC, Barcelona, Spain

⁴ Serra Hünter Fellow Programme, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, Spain

The use of irreversible electroporation (IRE) as a method for cardiac ablation in the treatment of cardiac arrhythmias, known as Pulsed Field Ablation (PFA), has rapidly moved from preclinical studies to clinic. One of the major advantages of this novel ablation technique over radiofrequency or cryoablation is safety. Although efficacy and long-term lesion durability have been demonstrated in limited groups of patients, studies in larger groups of individuals are still under development.

The reference indicator of acute lesion formation during cardiac ablation with thermal techniques consists in recording the local electrical activity changes with electroanatomical mapping systems.

In the case of PFA, the modifications produced in the reversible and irreversible damaged areas are still unknown. Of particular interest from a clinical perspective is to determine how and when the electrical activity of the reversible areas recovers after PFA. Studying the dynamics of this process can help to understand the optimal use of electroanatomical mapping systems in the PFA framework.

In this study we acquired high-density local electrograms before and during 60 min after PFA application. The measurements were performed in different points of the right and left ventricular epicardial surface of swine using an open chest approach following a protocol approved by the Sant Pau Hospital Animal Experimentation Ethical Committee. Under general anesthesia, a median sternotomy was made to create a surgical window. Unipolar electrograms were recorded using a 128-channel electrode matrix (BIOSEMI) attached to the epicardial surface (interelectrode distance=0.75 mm, total dimensions 9.5 × 9 mm). For PFA ablation, a monopolar catheter (Biosense Webster Thermocool STSF) was positioned in the region corresponding to the center of the electrode

array and a return electrode patch was attached to the back of the animals. After the procedure, and at least 3 hours from the last application, tissue was processed and lesion areas were stained with Triphenyltetrazolium Chloride (TTC) to assess acute lesion morphology.

Our results show an immediate change from basal narrow biphasic electrograms to wide monophasic electrograms with marked ST-segment elevation. Narrow QRS-complexes gradually reappear while ST-elevation recovers back to basal conditions from the periphery towards the center of the mapped area. The extent and dynamics of the observed changes depend on the voltage and the position, i. e., depend on the electric field intensity. After tissue staining, we observe that the area where the electrograms are modified is beyond the area of acute damage. This confirms that the electrical activity of the reversible electroporation area is also acutely modified. The preliminary analysis of the results suggest that the different recovery dynamics observed could help in differentiating between reversible and irreversible electroporation areas. This study could also help in establishing the optimal acute time for remapping after treatment.